

ASSESSMENT OF FOOT POSTURE INDEX AMONG BEAUTICIAN**Dr. Rutuja Ganesh Hadke*, Dr. Pooja Rathod**¹Intern DPOs Nett College of Physiotherapy, Thane.²Assistant Professor, DPOs Nett College of Physiotherapy, Thane.

Article Received on 18 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 15 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951132>

Corresponding Author*Dr. Rutuja Ganesh Hadke**

Intern DPOs Nett College of
Physiotherapy, Thane.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Rutuja Ganesh Hadke*, Dr. Pooja Rathod. (2025). ASSESSMENT OF FOOT POSTURE INDEX AMONG BEAUTICIAN. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 840-848.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Beauticians are exposed to various hazards in the workplace such as awkward posture, use of vibratory tools, repetitive movements and prolonged standing. Participants were 80 beauticians of age group 18-40 years. Foot posture was assessed using the foot posture index scale. Distribution analysis revealed that 62 participants (77.5%) had normal foot posture score, 13 (16.25%) had pronated foot posture and 5 (6.25%) had supinated foot posture. The study concluded that most beauticians possess normal foot posture, despite a notable proportion being overweight or obese. The present study suggests a need for the implementation of ergonomic modifications, postural education and strengthening foot exercises can help to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and improve occupational well-being among

beauticians.

KEYWORDS: foot posture index (FPI), body mass index (BMI).

INTRODUCTION

Beautician in the Cambridge dictionary has been as “a trained person whose work is to enhance the appearance of a client’s face, body and hair by means of makeup and beauty management. Prolong non-neutral posture, repetitive movements, working at a fast pace, general distress or prolonged standing periods make them vulnerable to musculoskeletal symptoms. Beauticians work has long hours and lack of adequate breaks during work which might cause fatigue and pain. Most common affected musculoskeletal disorders were knees, lower back, neck, ankles/feet in beauticians.^[1]

There can be different reason for pain such as postural strain repetitive movements, overuse and prolonged immobilization. Making a difference in your posture or poor body mechanics may give rise to spine alignment issues and muscle shortening and thus leading other muscle being misused and becoming painful. The blood flow will decreased if a muscle contract for a long time and this lead to accumulation of substances, thus raised level of substances cause irritation and pain.^[2]

A high prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders has been recorded among workers who are exposed to manual labour, work in unusual and restricted postures, repetitive and static work, cold temperature and vibrations.^[4] Foot posture index (FPI-6) is valid and moderately reliable tool to evaluate foot posture.^[5]

METHODOLOGY

The study was performed in south Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. It was observational study to assessed foot posture index among beauticians (add) ethical. A written inform consent was taken from the participants in the language better understood by them. Purpose of the study and procedure was explained earlier to the participants. Participants were 80 beauticians of age group 18-40 years excluding those who already been diagnosed with neurological symptoms, Severe cardiovascular or pulmonary disease (PVD, COPD, asthma and pulmonary TB etc.), recent surgery and fracture of lower limb. Selection of the participants was done as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Foot posture index (FPI-6) is valid and moderately reliable tool to evaluate foot posture.^[5] FPI used to assess the static foot alignment which has 6 items talar head palpation, observation of curve above and below the lateral malleolus, bulge in the region of talonavicular joint, eversion and inversion of calcaneus, congruence of the medial longitudinal arch and adduction and abduction of forefoot in relation to rear foot. Score between 0 to +5 indicate normal feet; +6 to +9 indicate pronated feet; >+10 indicate highly pronated feet; -1 to -4 indicate supinated feet; -5 to -12 indicate highly supinated feet.

RESULTS

The result indicates that while most beauticians maintain normal foot alignment, a considerable number are overweight, which may predispose them to altered lower limb biomechanics over time. Distribution analysis revealed that 62 participants (77.5%) had normal foot posture score, 13 (16.25%) had pronated foot posture and 5 (6.25%) had supinated foot posture. No severe postural deformities were observed. To test the normality

was done by using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test to check data is come from normal distribution, but not normally distributed.

1. Correlation between foot posture index & body mass index to investigate the relationship between FPI & BMI

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

		FPI	BMI
	Pearson Correlation	1	.846**
FPI	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	80	80
	Pearson Correlation	.846**	1
BMI	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	80	80

Fig. 1.

In this study we were considered FPI & BMI as two variable. Here obtained value for $r=0.846$ which indicates high positive correlation and value of $p=0.000$ ($p<0.01$) less than significance so can accept the alternative hypothesis.

2. Correlation between normal foot posture index & body mass index to investigate the relationship between FPI & BMI

		FPI (Normal)	BMI
	Pearson Correlation	1	.809**
FPI (Normal)	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	62	62
	Pearson Correlation	.809**	1
BMI	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	62	62

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig. 2.

In this study we were considered normal FPI & BMI are two variables, here obtained value for $r=0.809$ which also indicates high positive correlation & value of $p=0.000$ (<0.01) less than level of significance.

3. Correlation between pronated foot posture index & body mass index to investigate the relationship between pronated FPI & BMI.

		FPI (Pronated)	BMI
	Pearson Correlation	1	.517
FPI (Pronated)	Sig. (2-tailed)		.071
	N	13	13
	Pearson Correlation	.517	1
BMI	Sig. (2-tailed)	.071	
	N	13	13

Fig. 3.

In this study we were considered pronated FPI & BMI two variable, here obtained value for $r=0.517$ which indicates moderate positive correlation between these two variables and value for $p=0.071(>0.01)$ greater than level of significance so accepted the null hypothesis.

4. Correlation between supinated foot posture index & body mass index to investigate the relationship between supinated FPI & BMI

		FPI (Supinated)	BMI
	Pearson Correlation	1	.407
FPI (Supinated)	Sig. (2-tailed)		.497
	N	5	5
	Pearson Correlation	.407	1
BMI	Sig. (2-tailed)	.497	
	N	5	5

Fig. 4.

In this study we were considered supinated FPI & BMI are two variables, here obtained value for $r=0.407$ which indicates low positive correlation between these two variables and value of $p=0.497(>0.01)$ is greater than level of significance so and accepted the null hypothesis.

Variables	Body Mass Index	Significance (2-tailed)
FPI	0.846	0.000
FPI (Normal)	0.809	0.000
FPI (Pronated)	0.517	0.071
FPI (Supinated)	0.407	0.497

Fig. 5.

Above table shows values of correlation coefficient and p values {significance (2-tailed)} finally, it concluded that foot posture index significantly affects the body mass index (obesity) in beauticians, with increased in FPI with increases BMI (obesity) in beautician.

In statistics normality tests are used, to determine if data set is well-model by normal distribution to investigate that whether foot posture index score is normally distributed or not.

SPSS OUTPUT

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
FPI Score	80	100.0%	0	0.0%	80	100.0%

Fig. 6.

Descriptives				
			Statistic	Std. Error
FPI Score	Mean		2.813	.2733
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.268	
		Upper Bound	3.357	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.792	
	Median		3.000	
	Variance		5.977	
	Std. Deviation		2.4448	
	Minimum		-2.0	
	Maximum		8.0	
	Range		10.0	
	Interquartile Range		4.0	
	Skewness		.117	.269
	Kurtosis		-.991	.532

Fig. 7.

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FPI Score	.133	80	.001	.955	80	.007

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Fig. 8.

The above table shows the result of Kolmogorov-Smirnova & Shapiro-wilk test of normality (test of statistic, degree of freedom, p values). Since we have greater than 50 observations (N=80>50), we were interpreted the Kolmogorov-Smirnova test result.

One Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test which is non-parametric alternative to one sample t-test used to compare the median of a single sample to a hypothesized median value.

SPSS OUTPUT

Ranks			
	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Negative Ranks	34 ^a	32.50	1105.00
Positive Ranks	36 ^b	38.33	1380.00
FPI_Ref - FPI Score			
Ties	10 ^c		
Total	80		

FPI_Ref < FPI Score

FPI_Ref > FPI Score

FPI_Ref = FPI Score

Test Statistics ^a	
	FPI Ref - FPI Score
Z	-.812 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.417

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test Based on negative ranks

Fig. 9.

p-value provided by SPSS is .417 which is greater than 0.05 (i.e. alternative hypothesis. This indicates that “There is no significant difference in the Foot Posture Index score among beauticians OR The median FPI score of beauticians is equal to 3.

FPI Score	
Normal Foot	62
Pronated Foot	13
Supinated Foot	5

Fig. 10.

Fig. 11.

From the above doughnut chart, we can interpret that, 78% beauticians have normal foot posture while only 6% beauticians have supinated foot posture.

CLUSTERED COLUMN CHART SHOWING AGE WISE FOOT POSTURE IN BEAUTICIANS

Fig. 12.

Age Group	FPI Score		
	Normal Foot	Pronated Foot	Supinated Foot
21-25	18	0	3
26-30	22	1	2
31-35	12	5	0
36-40	10	7	0

Fig. 13.

From the above clustered column chart, we can interpret that, beauticians in the age group of 26-30 have highest frequency of normal foot posture while in the age group of 36-40 they have highest frequency of pronated foot posture and highest supinated foot posture beauticians found in the age group of 21-25.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the foot posture index among beauticians and to determine the prevalence of postural deviations associated with their occupational demands in south Mumbai. Eighty participants aged 18-40 years with 2 years of work

experience and practicing minimum 2 hours per day were included. The results revealed that the majority of participants exhibited normal foot posture 62(77.5%), with smaller proportion showing pronated 13(16.25%) and supinated 5(6.25%) postures. The mean body mass index (BMI) of 25.8kg/m² falls within overweight range, suggesting that beautician may be at potential risk for biomechanical stress on lower limb.

Another study was conducted by Neha P Patel et al. to find out association between work related musculoskeletal disorders and fatigue among female beauticians in Ahmedabad an observational study.^[1] The result of the correlation analysis in this study showed a moderate positive association between work related MSK disorder and occupational fatigue ($r=0.658$, $p<0.001$). This indicated that participants who experienced higher level of MSK discomfort, also reported higher level of fatigue. An observational analytical cross-sectional study was conducted among 80 female beauticians in Ahmedabad, Gujrat using purposive sampling. Participants aged 18-40 years with at least 2 years of work experience and practicing minimum 2 hours per day were included. The Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire (NMQ) was administered to assess MSK symptoms in nine body regions, and multidimensional assessment of fatigue (MAF) scale was used to measured fatigue. The mean age of participants was 31.69 +- 5.65 years. A high prevalence of work related MSK disorder was observed, the findings showed that considerable proportion of participants reported MSK pain in multiple body region such as 36% reported neck pain, 29% had shoulder pain, 14% had elbow pain, 23% had wrist pain, 22% had upper back pain, 45% had lower back pain, 63% had knee pain and 34% experienced ankle or foot pain. The result of the correlation analysis in this study showed a moderate positive association between work related MSK disorder and occupational fatigue ($r=0.658$, $p<0.001$). This indicated that participants who experienced higher level of MSK discomfort, also reported higher level of fatigue.

A similar study was conducted by HUDA ANJUM et al. 1 to determine the frequency of musculoskeletal problems in beauticians of Rawalpindi and Islamabad.^[2] A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted using self- structured questionnaire which was generated after literature review. 300 beauticians were considered for data collection which revealed that 66% of them having pain due to prolong standing sampling technique used was purposive sampling. Beautician with age range of 20-45 years were included in this study. A questionnaire consisted of closed ended questions, it was a visual tool to assess the posture and muscle work. Data was analyzed by SPSS21. 173(66%) of beauticians reported their pain

was due to prolonged standing and pain in ankle was reported by 58(45.9%) of the beauticians.

CONCLUSION

This study conclude that most beauticians possess normal foot posture, despite a notable proportion being overweight or obese. 77.5% of them having normal foot posture, 16.25% having pronated foot posture & 6.25% having supinated foot posture.

Most participants in this study demonstrated normal foot posture, but the occupational strain will lead to progressive postural deviation over time.

The present study suggests a need for the implementation of ergonomic modifications, postural education and strengthening foot exercises can help to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and improve occupational well-being among beauticians.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank the beautician participants for their valuable cooperation, which made this research possible at South Mumbai, Maharashtra.

REFERENCES

1. Neha P Patel, Dhara S Soni, Rutvi M Talaviya, Roshani P Tank, Mayank S Solanki. Association Between Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders And Fatigue Among Beauticians In Ahmedabad: An Abservational Study, June 2023; 13(6). ISSN: 2249-9571.
2. Huda Anjum, Wardah Qazi, Hadiya Rehman, Muhammad Saad Shafique. Frequency Of Musculoskeletal Problems In Beauticians Of Rawalpindi And Islambad. PJMHS22168490. August 2022; 16.
3. Alexandra Tsigonia, Dimitra Tanagra, Athena Linos, Georgios Merakoulis And Evangelos C. Alexopoulos. Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Heath 27th November 2009; 6: 2967-2979.
4. Harshita Gowda, Steffi. P. Mascarenhas, Dnyanesh Pramod Patil, Unnati Patil. International Jounal Science And Research ISSNl: 2249-9571, December 2016; 6(12): 8TH.
5. Jiaman Yang, Zhiwen Ou, Zhitao Mao, Yi Wang, Yiheng Zhong, Wie Dong, Zhen Shen, Zehua Chen. Reliability And Validity Of Foot Posture Index (FPI-6) For Evaluating Foot Posture In Participants With Low Back Pain. Scientific Reports, 2022; 12(1): 21168.